

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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IMPLEMENTATION OF THE EDINBURGH POSTNATAL DEPRESSION SCALE
AT A PSYCHIATRIC AMBULATORY CLINIC

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

We evaluated the use of the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) as a screening tool to prevent the misdiagnosis of Postpartum Depression (PPD). The Stetler Model (SM) was used to guide implementation of the EPDS in an ambulatory psychiatric setting for this quality improvement (QI) project. Women diagnosed with PPD during an eight-week period immediately prior to the implementation of the EPDS were compared with women diagnosed with PPD using the EPDS during an eight-week period. The final sample of participating key stakeholders included three Psychiatrists (MD) and one Nurse Practitioner (NP) that agreed to implement the EPDS. A total of 29 pre- and post implementation postpartum women (PPW) met inclusion criteria for this project making up the final sample size. Eight were not screened by the EPDS during the two-week period prior to its implementation. A total of 21 postpartum women were screened with implementation of the EPDS. Of those PPW, 21 (100%) were diagnosed with PPD compared to six/eight (75%) PPW diagnosed with PPD without the use of the EPDS. Participating MDs and the NP diagnosed two (25%) patients with non-postpartum depression and anxiety when the EPDS was not used. Screening for postpartum depression with a tool that supports measurement of symptoms may help to more accurately diagnose PPD, and thus with more appropriate treatment of PPD.

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BACKGROUND

PPD is a serious mental illness that affects 13% of women (O'Hara & Swain, 2009). In the United States, one out of ten women aged 18 to 44 experienced symptoms of major depressive disorder (MDD) in the past year (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2017). Globally, this rate affects one in eight women and the rates can be higher in lower and middle income countries (Stewart & Vigod, 2016). In the United States, inner city women, mothers of pre-term infants, and adolescents have the highest risk for PPD. Pregnant women with a history of tobacco, alcohol and illicit drug use also have an increased likelihood of PPD (Sit & Wisner, 2009). PPD can affect daily functioning and can last less than a month to years thus becoming a chronic problem (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2017). It is therefore imperative that healthcare providers begin screening for PPD after birth in order to detect it before it becomes severe.

PPD is evaluated and diagnosed based upon the criteria outlined in the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*, 5th edition (DSM-5). A diagnosis of PPD begins with the diagnosis of MDD, which is then labeled PPD because the women has given birth to a child. MDD typically occurs within four weeks of delivery and is referred to as “with peri-partum onset,” however, PPD can manifest up to 12 months after childbirth (Stewart & Vigod, 2016). Symptoms of PPD include sleep disturbance, anxiety, irritability, feeling overwhelmed, intrusive thoughts regarding the baby’s health, suicidal ideations and homicidal ideations. Mothers with PPD may exhibit other behaviors that can have adverse effects on the infant including being withdrawn, disengaged, and non-interacting. These behaviors can lead to neglect of the child

resulting in the child suffering from cognitive, behavioral, emotional and developmental disturbances (Dennis & McQueen, 2009). Postpartum Depression may also result in paternal depression, as depression in one partner can cause depression in the other (Cameron, Sedov, & Tomfohr-Madsen, 2016). Due to a higher frequency of relational and financial stressors, PPD occurs more frequently among African Americans and Hispanics when compared with Whites and Asian/Pacific Islanders (Liu, Giallo, Doan, Seidman, & Tronick, 2016).

In a study conducted by Stewart & Vigod, (2016) in which the EPDS was used, the researcher found that the EPDS successfully detected PPD as evidenced by a sensitivity of approximately 0.80 and specificity of 0.90 using a cutoff score of 13. The EPDS is a self-report tool consisting of 10 items ranked from zero to three, which assesses the patient's symptoms over the past week. The maximum score is 30 and depression is suspected at a score of 10 or greater, while a score ≥ 13 indicates a risk for MDD. Screening should be completed at every visit for up to 1 year postpartum.

In the Southern California psychiatric ambulatory clinic of interest NPs and MDs do not use a standardized method to screen women for PPD. Utilizing the EPDS as a screening tool can help NPs and MDs identify women with PPD, thus decreasing the potential of missing this critical diagnosis. At this psychiatric clinic PPW have been diagnosed during their intake appointment with vague diagnoses (e.g., unspecified anxiety disorder, and unspecified depressive disorder). These vague diagnoses do not adequately represent the severity of anxiety and depression as would the diagnosis of PPD. Correctly diagnosing PPW with PPD is vital because these women are at risk of harming themselves as well as their babies. The EPDS can guide treatment options that

may include psychotherapy, psychotropic medications, or a combination of these treatments based on the score obtained. Furthermore, if used at all follow-up visits, the EPDS score can facilitate evaluation of scores over time, and thus be used to evaluate and guide follow up and treatment. The purpose of this QI project is to implement and evaluate the feasibility and clinical appropriateness of the EPDS tool in an ambulatory psychiatric setting using the SM.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Theoretical frameworks guide clinical projects by providing direction about where to begin and what to do (Bonnel & Smith, 2014). The SM is a critical thinking model with interactive and criteria based decision making steps. It guides problem solving in determining the applicability of research and evidence in regard to practice related issues as well as how to implement and evaluate evidence. This model is a practitioner oriented model that not only applies to individuals but also to project teams (Stetler, 2010).

The SM was developed out of the need to teach the implementation of evidenced based practices (EBP) to nursing students and staff. It has evolved over the decades into published resources and tools (Stetler, 2010). The latest version updated in 2009, has two parts and five phases. The SM has been utilized in both academic and clinical settings including acute care, ambulatory and long term care and has led to cost saving strategies (Stetler, 2010). The SM identifies stakeholders as faculty, advanced practice nurses and staff nurses since they are the implementers of the EBPs (Stetler, 2010). Specht, Bergquist, & Frantz (1995) reported using the model to guide treatment of pressure ulcers resulting in better patient outcomes and decreased costs. Snyder, Facchiano, & Brewer, (2011), reported that NPs have utilized the model to determine the best method of assessing anxiety in patients with Parkinson's disease. NP's were able to engage in the knowledge search process to gather information regarding Parkinson's disease and anxiety. Figure 1 below depicts the SM and its components. In the following sections a description of SM's components is presented.

Figure 1. Stetler model (Stetler, 2010).

Phase I: Preparation

The first phase of the SM involves identification of the problem to be solved. Once this is completed, research data and supplemental evidence are sorted and evaluated. Influential factors and affirming priorities are considered when attempting to solve the identified problem. This involves identifying factors that can impede or facilitate problem solving (Stetler, 2010). The researcher must also consider the expected outcome as part of the problem solving process in order to determine if the problem to be solved is valued by stakeholders.

For this project, the university librarian assisted with literature searches to generate focused results on PPD and the EPDS upon which practice can be based. The research problem identified is the lack of use of a standardized tool to help psychiatric mental health practitioners including NPs and MDs, to identify PPD in a southern California, psychiatric ambulatory clinic. To better understand the EPDS tool and its

potential uses, a thorough literature review was completed. Issues surrounding users, including NPs and MDs, and factors that may influence their practice relevant to PPD were explored.

Phase II: Validation

In the second phase, the evidence for credibility, applicability, and operational details are assessed (Stetler, 2010). This is achieved by appraising the research to determine the quality of evidence. Validity is also evaluated using statistical analysis of sensitivity, specificity and confidence intervals that help identify clinical significance (Stetler, 2010).

Phase III: Comparative Evaluation/Decision Making

In the third phase, findings are evaluated for desirability and feasibility for application to practice. Risk factors are determined, resources needed are identified and the readiness of others involved is considered (Stetler, 2010). The implementation of the EPDS is assumed to have little risk to most stakeholders that include NPs, MDs, as well as patients. Use of the EPDS is feasible and cost effectiveness. It can be printed from the internet free of charge, is easy to complete and is available in various languages. However, there may be potential challenges for implementation of the EPDS. One challenge is that clerical staff may forget to distribute the EPDS to patients. Another challenge is that patients may not want to devote time to complete the EPDS that can take a few minutes.

Phase IV: Translation/Application

The fourth phase involves translating the findings into practice at the individual, group or department/organization level (Stetler, 2010). In a study with a somewhat

similar application of SM, Snyder, Facchiano & Brewer (2011) examined NPs recognition of anxiety in Parkinson's disease patients using the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HARS). They used HARS in an outpatient clinic to improve recognition of anxiety in Parkinson's disease (Snyder et al., 2011).

Phase V: Evaluation

The fifth phase, is focused on assessing whether the EBP change met the desired outcomes, whether it should be integrated into practice, and at what level it may be implemented, e.g. the institutional or individual level (Stetler, 2010). An evaluation of the feasibility and clinical usefulness of the EPDS is necessary to determine if adaptation is justifiable. Table 1 below describes how each phase of the SM will be utilized for implementation of the EPDS to identify PPD in a psychiatric ambulatory clinic.

Table 1

Plan for Implementation of the Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale to Identify Postpartum Depression at a Psychiatric Ambulatory Setting

Phase I: Preparation	Phase II: Validation	Phase III: Comparative Evaluation/Decision Making	Phase IV: Translation/Application	Phase V: Evaluation
<p>Lack of use of a screening tool (e.g. EPDS) to help NPs and MDs identify PPD.</p> <p>Explore issues surrounding users and factors influencing their practice.</p> <p>Partner with a research specialist to assist with literature searches.</p>	<p>Identify the evidence and appraise the research for credibility, applicability, and operational details based on the quality of evidence.</p>	<p>Evaluate the feasibility of research and resources.</p> <p>Determine risk factors to stakeholders: clerical staff, NPs and MDs, clinic and patients.</p> <p>Assess readiness of stakeholders. Clerical staff can handout the tool to patients to complete. Then NPs and MDs can review the tool that is free of charge to use and can be printed off the internet.</p>	<p>Present research findings on PPD and the EPDS to the NPs and MDs via committee and individual meetings.</p> <p>The NPs and MDs decide to implement the EPDS screening tool.</p>	<p>Provide statistical analysis of the total sample size based on how many NPs and MDs implemented the EPDS.</p> <p>The number of patients that were screened and identified with PPD.</p> <p>The goal is that the NPs and MDs, permanently implement the EPDS to enhance mental health outcomes of women with PPD if the project evaluation is positive.</p>

Note: EPDS = Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale; NPs = Nurse Practitioner; MDs = Medical Doctors; PPD = Postpartum Depression.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of the literature (ROL) was conducted utilizing the following databases: CINAHL, EBSCO, PubMed, ScienceDirect, Cochrane Library and PsycINFO. In addition, a reference list of articles was mined in order to identify potential resources not identified by the database searches. Key words and key word combinations included: postpartum depression, Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale, screening, prevention and treatment. Article abstracts were reviewed for relevance to the current project. Peer reviewed articles published from 2009 to 2017 and written in English language were included in the ROL. Articles focused on depression during pregnancy were excluded. The ROL was organized around the following themes: pathophysiology, prevention, treatment, psychotherapy, psychotropic medications, screening tools, the Patient Health Questionnaire, the Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale, comparison of screening tools and justification for using The Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale.

The search was effective in finding 42 relevant articles on postpartum depression and its treatment as well as screening tools including the EPDS. Articles were analyzed if their focus appeared relevant by title and abstract. After applying exclusion criteria, 14 articles were included in the ROL. Of these, three were systemic reviews, two were prospective studies, four were quantitative, four were literature reviews and one was a clinical case study. The upcoming sections will cover basic information about PPD followed by a discussion of the identified evidence.

Pathophysiology of Postpartum Depression

The pathophysiology of PPD is not fully understood. Contributing factors may be genetic susceptibility, epigenetic phenomena, hormonal changes, psychological

problems, social problems and stressful events (Viguera, 2016). Genetic factors can cause some women to be more vulnerable to PPD. If a sibling has had an episode of PPD, the risk for the other sibling increases fourfold. After birth, women have increased sensitivity to hormonal fluctuations of estrogen, progesterone, cortisol, melatonin, oxytocin and thyroid. Changes in serum concentrations of these hormones are associated with PPD. Abnormal neurotransmitter levels and activity are also involved in the pathogenesis of postpartum depression. The enzyme monoamine oxidase-A in the prefrontal and anterior cingulate cortex is elevated in women with PPD. This enzyme rapidly metabolizes neurotransmitters including dopamine, norepinephrine and serotonin, potentially leading to depression. Other aspects of brain function may be altered in PPD. For example, the differences in the activity of certain genes in the hippocampus may increase vulnerability to PPD by causing women to be more sensitive to the drop in estrogen occurring after delivery (Viguera, 2016; Miller & LaRusso, 2011).

Prevention

Early identification of women at risk for PPD is vital in the prevention of the development of this debilitating condition. Women who have untreated depression during pregnancy are seven times more likely to develop PPD (Miller & LaRusso, 2011; Stewart & Vigod, 2016). Identification of women at risk begins with an evaluation of their mental health history for depression, including premenstrual dysphoric disorder, and family history of depression. It is also important to assess the mother-to-be, about current and past stressors, social support system, feelings about their pregnancy and motherhood in order to determine their risk for PPD (Miller & LaRusso, 2011).

Secondary and tertiary prevention involve early detection and treatment of depressive symptoms after birth. Screening tools such as the EPDS that has extensive validation in the postpartum population, or the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) that has extensive validation in primary care settings can be utilized (Miller & LaRusso, 2011; Stewart & Vigod, 2016). Tertiary prevention also include evaluation of mother-infant interaction and the mother's caretaking skills to identify specific interventions that may be needed to support parenting and bonding (Miller & LaRusso, 2011).

The literature supports specific interventions based on a client's identified symptoms of PPD. When a woman has a history of medication response to depression especially during the postpartum period, starting an antidepressant before or just after birth may be indicated (Miller & LaRusso, 2011; Stewart & Vigod, 2016). Psychotherapy is beneficial if a woman is struggling with the transition to motherhood. Nutritional deficiencies should be addressed through education and counseling regarding specific supplements related to PPD. Deficiencies in n-3 EFA, folate and iron can contribute to depression. Physical activity may reduce the risk of PPD therefore the American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology recommends a minimum of 30 minutes of moderate daily exercise for PPW. Since sleep deprivation is a potent predictor of PPD it is important to educate women regarding sleep hygiene and the use of sleep aide medication that may help prevent PPD (Miller & LaRusso, 2011; Stewart & Vigod, 2016). Breastfeeding can be stressful for some women, and can cause early termination of the practice therefore it is important for women to have lactation support. Pregnancy can be a difficult change in a women's life. Approximately half of pregnancies worldwide are unintended thus

increasing the risk of PPD (Miller & LaRusso, 2011). Counseling regarding birth control methods as well as family planning with the women's partner is vital.

Treatment

Cognitive Behavioral Therapy

Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is a short-term form of psychotherapy that combines components from cognitive therapy and behavioral therapy. The purpose of CBT is to have an individual identify and challenge distorted thinking by teaching techniques and skills to change negative behaviors. Studies have found that CBT is an effective individual psychotherapy treatment for PPD. CBT is provided in one hour sessions that can also be utilized in a group setting (Van Lieshout et al., 2017; Werner, Miller, Osborne, Kuzava, & Monk, 2015). CBT is taught using a manual that guides treatment, allowing psychiatric providers from multiple disciplines that include MDs, NPs and therapists to use it in the hospital and community setting (Van Lieshout, Yang, Haber, & Ferro, 2017).

CBT has been shown to have clinical significance in decreasing depressive symptoms, and in improving social support, mother-infant bonding, and partner relationships (Van Lieshout et al., 2017). In a study that included 34 women with PPD who completed a nine week CBT group, 80% of participants showed clinically significant improvement in depressive symptoms (Van Lieshout et al., 2017). However, one systemic review of CBT as a treatment for women with PPD showed mixed results with six studies reporting success and six studies showing no effect of CBT (Werner et al., 2015). Another study tested whether CBT was an effective treatment for PPD that included 21 participants who received CBT and completed the EPDS at baseline and then

again in seven to ten weeks. The results from this study indicated a reduction of the EPDS scores that averaged 6.24 points compared to participants in the control group that averaged 2.42 points at seven to ten weeks after receiving CBT showing it's effectiveness in the treatment of PPD (Pugh, Hadjistavropoulos, & Dirkse, 2016).

Interpersonal Therapy

Postpartum depression can have an adverse impact on the mother and infant, especially when struggling with the transition to motherhood. Interpersonal therapy (IPT) can not only be used to treat PPD but can also help prevent it. IPT is based on Bowlby's Attachment and Sullivan's IPT that is the foundation for understanding how people form and maintain relationships (Miniati et al., 2014; Stuart, 2012). This form of therapy is brief and can be conducted individually or in the group setting (Miller & LaRusso, 2011). IPT is a first-line evidenced based treatment for mild to severe depression. It is a time limited, dynamically informed psychotherapy that is designed to decrease symptoms and improve interpersonal functioning. Interpersonal distress is linked to the symptoms of depression. The targets of treatment are psychiatric symptoms, interpersonal relationships and social support.

Maladaptive behaviors cause difficulties in interpersonal relationships. IPT conceptualizes the patient's behaviors based on temperament, personality and attachment style as well as biological factors and physiological functioning in the context of social relationships and support. It follows a family medicine model of care with short-term treatment for acute distress and maintenance treatment to prevent relapse (Stuart, 2012).

A prospective cohort study to test the feasibility, effectiveness and acceptability of IPT to treat PPD included 41 women in the treatment group and 20 women in the

control group (Posmontier, Neugebauer, Stuart, Chittams, & Shaughnessy, 2016). The treatment group received IPT and was evaluated at eight weeks and then again at 12 weeks compared to the control group. The results showed depression was significantly lower among women in the treatment group compared to the control group (Week 8, $P = .047$; Week 12, $P = .029$) (Posmontier et al., 2016). Another study utilizing a randomized controlled trial of 205 pregnant women at risk for PPD were randomized to IPT, with 104 in the treatment group and 101 in the control group. Six months later the women that received IPT had a depression rate of 16% compared to the control group that had 31% (Zlotnick, Tzilos, Miller, Seifer, & Stout, 2016). Both of these studies provide evidence that IPT is an effective treatment option for PPD.

Psychotropic Medication

There are a variety of reasons used to medicate women with PPD. Antidepressant medication is recommended when symptoms of PPD do not respond to psychotherapy, when symptoms are severe, or when it is preferred by the patient. Patients with PPD who have had a history of depression or PPD where there was a positive response to an antidepressant may also be prescribed medication. Sertraline is typically the first medication used to treat patients with PPD because it does not pass into breast milk at high levels compared to other antidepressants (Miller & LaRusso, 2011; Stewart & Vigod, 2016). Most selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) are relatively safe because less than 10% of the maternal dose passes into the breast milk. These medications may be considered for treating mothers breastfeeding healthy, full term infants (Stewart & Vigod, 2016).

A Cochrane review that included three randomized control trials comparing SSRIs to a placebo group, evaluated the effectiveness of antidepressants in women with PPD. The researchers found a response to SSRIs at a rate of 52.2% compared to 36.5% of those receiving placebo, and a remission rate for SSRIs of 46.0% compared to 25.7% of those receiving placebo (Stewart & Vigod, 2016).

It is recommended that once symptoms of depression are in remission, antidepressants should be continued for six to 12 months to reduce the risk of relapse. After this timeframe, antidepressants are to be tapered off for the first episode of depression. However, for recurrent episodes of depression, treatment with medications may be indefinite (Miller & LaRusso, 2011; Stewart & Vigod, 2016).

Screening Tools

The Patient Health Questionnaire

The PHQ-9 is a nine item self-report depression screening tool used to evaluate symptoms experienced over a two-week period. It has two possible scoring methods that include a summary scoring algorithm and a diagnostic algorithm. In non-prenatal women a score ≥ 10 on a scale ranging from 0–27 indicates MDD. The diagnostic algorithm scoring is based on DSM-5 MDD diagnostic criteria. The criteria include the presence of at least five depressive symptoms. One of these symptoms must be depressed mood or loss of interest occurring most of the day nearly every day for at least two weeks. In primary care settings, the PHQ-9 has been frequently used and recommended for depression screening. It has been translated into at least 25 languages worldwide. The PHQ-9 can be used to screen for PPD as well as non-postpartum depression in the adult population. (Flynn, Sexton, Ratliff, Porter, & Zivin, 2011).

The Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale

The EPDS is a commonly used 10 item self-report perinatal specific depression screening tool to evaluate symptoms experienced over a one-week period. It was developed for use in PPW because it deemphasizes somatic symptoms that can overlap with depressive symptoms, considered normal during the postpartum period (Flynn et al., 2011).

The EPDS is recommended by the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists and the American Academy of Pediatrics to identify PPD (Stewart & Vigod, 2016). A score of ≥ 10 is the screening cut off for major and minor depression, while ≥ 13 is specific to screening for MDD only. It has been well studied and is the most commonly used tool to evaluate PPD worldwide (Flynn et al., 2011; van der Zee-van den Berg, Boere-Boonekamp, IJzerman, Haasnoot-Smallegange, & Reijneveld, 2017). A study of 264 women in which the EPDS was utilized as a screening tool resulted in 44 (16.7%) having PPD based on an EPDS score of ≥ 12 . Out of the 44 identified women with PPD, 82.4% met DSM-5 criteria verifying a high validity of the EPDS as a diagnostic tool for PPD (Gaillard, Le Strat, Mandelbrot, Keïta, & Dubertret, 2014).

Comparison of Screening Tools

Both the EPDS and the PHQ-9 are relatively easy to complete. The United States Preventive Services Task Force (2016) conducted systemic reviews that included 23 studies. Sensitivity ranging from 0.67 (95% CI, 0.18-0.96) to 1.00 (95% CI, 0.67-1.00) and specificity consistently at 0.87 or higher were reported. In contrast, data is sparse for the PHQ-9 in PPD, and specificity and sensitivity were generally not reported (O'Connor, Rossom, Henninger, Groom, & Burda, 2016). The validity of the PHQ-9 for identifying

PPD specifically has not been adequately studied although it has been extensively studied in non-postpartum populations as a depression screening tool. The report from a systematic review of the PHQ-9 in predicting general depression indicated sensitivity scores that ranged between 71% to 84% and specificity of 90% to 97%. One potential benefit of utilizing the PHQ-9 is that it will allow comparing results from screenings to other medical units or clinics where it has been used (Flynn et al., 2011).

Justification for using The Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale

Comparison between the EPDS and the PHQ-9 shows that the EPDS has more evidence to support its usefulness in screening for PPD. Insufficient evidence was found on the PHQ-9 for use in the postpartum population overall but the PHQ-9 was found to be valid and reliable screening tool for non-postpartum depression. The EPDS is recommended as the screening tool of choice for PPD by the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists and the American Academy of Pediatrics. It helps prevent delay of diagnosis of PPD through early detection (Miller & LaRusso, 2011; Stewart & Vigod, 2016). There is insufficient research on the PHQ-9 for use in the postpartum population and further research is needed to address it.

Summary

Although prevention strategies for PPD have been identified, there are still gaps in the literature. While following a healthy diet to prevent nutritional deficiencies, engaging in regular exercise, and adequate sleep are recommended there is limited evidence on whether these interventions reduce the risk of PPD therefore, more research is needed to validate the extent to which these strategies may help decrease PPD (Stewart & Vigod, 2016).

Not only are reports on the effectiveness of CBT in PPD inconsistent but little is known about its effectiveness in this population. The Van Lieshout et al. study (2017), was a nine-week study that reported positive results. However, a small sample size was used and a control group was not used therefore, the level of evidence emerging from this study was weak. The Pugh et al. study (2016) provided strong evidence of the effectiveness of CBT through a randomized control trial, even though a small sample size was used. Further studies with larger sample sizes are needed.

Posmontier et al. (2016) and Zlotnick et al. (2016) provided evidence on the effectiveness of IPT to prevent and treat PPD. That study had an adequate sample size and control groups that resulted in statistically significant reductions of PPD. However, the lack of randomization and utilizing only Black or Hispanic women means that results may not be generalizable to a heterogeneous sample of women.

The evidence that antidepressants can be beneficial in the treatment of PPD is compelling however exposure to antidepressants through breast milk may have serious consequences for the infant. Although current research supports antidepressant use for PPD more research is needed to investigate its long-term effects (Brummelte & Galea, 2016; Stewart & Vigod, 2016).

METHODS

Design

The purpose of this QI project is to examine the feasibility and effectiveness of using the EPDS to identify PPD in a psychiatric ambulatory clinic setting. The Stetler's five step model of preparation, validation, comparative evaluation/decision making, translation/application, and evaluation guided the implementation of the EPDS to screen patients for PPD.

Ethical Considerations

Approval for this project was obtained from the psychiatric clinic's Chief of Psychiatry. This project does not amount to the level of research on human subjects to create new knowledge as determined by the Institutional Review Boards (IRB) at California State University, Los Angeles. Full disclosure of the implementation of the EPDS was provided to the key stakeholders at the psychiatric ambulatory clinic. NPs and MDs were encouraged to use the EPDS to evaluate PPD, and their participation in all aspects of implementing the EPDS was voluntary. The Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) author is an employee of the organization where the project was conducted. Data were evaluated in aggregate.

Setting/Participants

This QI project took place at a psychiatric clinic in Fontana where an average of 200 to 250 predominately middle-class patients are seen daily. Most patients speak English and are either Caucasian or Hispanic and vary in age across the lifespan. Key stakeholders include NPs, MDs, patients and clerical staff.

Participants in the project were a convenience sample of NPs and MDs working in the psychiatric ambulatory clinic. Inclusion criteria to participate in the project are NPs and MDs who work full-time or part-time at the clinic and provide direct patient care. The NPs and MDs that work per diem were excluded from participation. This project also included a purposive sample of women that are patients at the psychiatric ambulatory clinic. Inclusion criteria are women 18 years of age or older who are English speaking and have given birth within the previous 12 months.

Procedures

In accordance with the SM, each of the five phases was used to guide the implementation of this project. The Preparation, Validation, Comparative Evaluation/Decision Making phases were completed as part of the review of literature. The Translation/Application phase was completed as part of the procedures.

The investigator encouraged NPs, MDs, and clerical staff to attend an information session on using the EPDS screening tool for PPD. Sessions were held at noon on a convenient day and lunch was provided. At information sessions research findings on PPD, the EPDS and use and scoring of the EPDS was presented via Power Point and handouts. The role of the clerical staff was also explained. This included placing one copy of the EPDS in the chart of each PPW. Socioeconomic factors including age, race/ethnicity, marital status, employment status and education were added to the back of the form by clerical staff that obtained this information from charts. The PPWs time from birth to time being seen by the provider was also added. The completed EPDS form was used by the MDs and NP to help identify PPD and to plan appropriate treatment. Identifying information such as patient names and medical record numbers were not

placed on the EPDS form and instead a number was linked to each form. The EPDS forms were kept in a locked box in the clinic chart room and only the DNP student had access to this locked box.

Evaluation Plan

This project culminated in an evaluation of the use of the EPDS to identify PPD. Toward this end the number of diagnosed PPD for the prior eight weeks without using the EPDS was compared with the number of diagnosed PPD using the EPDS over an eight-week period. Based on findings a decision to implement regular use of the EPDS at this same clinic will be made by the DNP student and MDs at the clinic. Socioeconomic factors of these patients included race/ethnicity, marital status, employment status and education. Also the number of weeks from birth to time being seen by the provider was recorded.

Table 2

Timeline

Completion Date	Task
May 2017	Proposal Defense
June 2017	Submit IRB application to California State University Los Angeles
August 2017	Informational sessions with key stakeholders via committee and individual meetings to obtain support
September – October 2017	Implement EPDS and collect data
November 2017	Manage and Analyze data
April 2018	Presentation of Findings Final Defense

PROJECT PRODUCT/RESULTS

This chapter presents the results of the data analysis including quantitative EPDS scores and socioeconomic factors. The dates of data collection for the number of women diagnosed with PPD over an eight-week period before the implementation of the EPDS was July 10, 2017 – September 1, 2017. The dates for data collection for the number of women diagnosed with PPD after the implementation of the EPDS over an eight-week period was September 4, 2017 – October 27, 2017. The final sample size for participating key stakeholders included three MDs and one NP (DNP Student) that decided to implement the EPDS. A total of 29 PPW met inclusion criteria for this project making up the final sample size. Eight were not screened by the EPDS during the time it was not implemented and 21 were screened after implementation of the EPDS.

Of the eight PPW that were not screened by the EPDS, six were diagnosed with PPD and two were diagnosed with non-postpartum depression with anxiety. The time from birth these PPW were diagnosed with PPD or non-postpartum depression with anxiety ranged from five to 12 weeks. Racially there were three Caucasians, three Hispanics, two African Americans and zero Asians. Six women were married, one was single and one was divorced. Five women were employed and three were unemployed. Two women had a high school education and six had a college level education.

Depression is suspected when the EPDS score is 10 or greater, and a score ≥ 13 indicates a risk for MDD. The 21 PPW that were screened by the EPDS had scores that ranged from 10 – 27 and all were diagnosed with PPD by the participating MDs two to 22 weeks from birth. Hispanics represented the highest number of PPW with nine participants. There were seven Caucasians, three African Americans and two Asians.

There were 10 married women, nine were single and two were divorced while 17 women were employed and four were unemployed. Eight women had a high school education and 13 went to college.

Table 3

Postpartum Women and Socioeconomic Factors (N = 29)

Characteristic	N	%
Race		
Asian	2	7
Black	5	17
Hispanic	14	48
White	8	28
Marital Status		
Married	16	55
Single	10	35
Divorced	3	10
Employment Status		
Employed	22	76
Unemployed	7	24
Education Level		
Highschool	10	35
College	19	65

Figure 2. Pre and post implementation of the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression scale.

LIMITATIONS

There are evident limitations to the generalizability of this project. The findings may not be generalizable because the project was conducted in a single psychiatric ambulatory clinic. There were time constraints for the project, as it was completed over an eight-week period.

The participating MDs and NP were not necessarily representative of the overall MDs and NPs at the clinic. Convenience sampling of MDs and NPs produced a small sample size that represents a bias in the data. Furthermore, the purposive sample of PPW at this clinic was also small. PPW inclusion criteria was up to 12 months after birth. However, the PPW in this project ranged from two to 22 weeks because there were no PPW beyond 22 weeks that met inclusion criteria. Not all PPW in the clinic during this project were included because other MDs and NPs that did not participate may have also seen PPW. This may explain why there was only 8 PPW in the pre-implementation phase compared to 21 PPW in the post-implementation phase of the EPDS.

IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE/RECOMMENDATIONS

Phase I: Preparation

Research data and supplemental evidence were searched, sorted and selected thorough a literature review on the EPDS in relation to psychiatric disorders. The misdiagnosis of PPD is a problem that is occurring at this psychiatric clinic. Vague diagnoses e.g., unspecified anxiety disorder and unspecified depressive disorder do not adequately represent the severity of anxiety and depression as would the diagnosis of PPD. Correctly diagnosing PPD is vital because these women are at risk of untoward outcomes including harming themselves as well as their babies.

Phase II: Validation

The literature on the EPDS was appraised and it was determined to be a credible, applicable and valid tool for identifying PPD.

Phase III: Comparative Evaluation/Decision Making

Research data provided evidence that the EPDS is a feasible screening tool therefore the decision was made that it would be implemented in this psychiatric clinic. The EPDS was assumed to have little risk to most stakeholders that included NPs, MDs, patients, and clerical staff. Clerical staff provided the EPDS to patients to complete, then NPs and MDs would review it. The EPDS that requires little time and effort to complete was printed from the internet free of charge.

Phase IV: Translation/Application

The DNP student held information sessions for the clerical staff and the NPs and MDs on the EPDS screening tool for PPD. There was a total of seven clerical staff, nine

MDs and one NP in attendance. Of this all seven clerical staff, three MDs and one NP decided to participate in this project.

Phase V: Evaluation

This sample of 29 PPW of which 27 (93%) were diagnosed with PPD was very diverse. It included women of all ethnicities that vary in marital status, employment status and education. These results provide evidence that PPD can affect women regardless of their socioeconomic factors. Although most women were Hispanic totaling 14 (48%), this may be due to a higher Hispanic population receiving care at this clinic compared with other ethnicities. Regardless of whether these women were single 10 (35%) or married 16 (55%), PPD affected both groups. Most women 22 (76%) were employed with education levels ranging from high school to college.

This QI project using quantitative methods implemented and evaluated the feasibility and clinical appropriateness of the EPDS tool in an ambulatory psychiatric setting using the SM. Key findings include 21 (100%) PPW that were diagnosed with PPD using the EPDS compared to 6 (75%) of PPW that were diagnosed with PPD without the use of the EPDS. Participating MDs and NP diagnosed 2 (25%) patients with non-postpartum depression with anxiety when the EPDS was not used. If these patients were screened with the EPDS they may have been more accurately diagnosed with PPD.

Overall implementation of the EPDS went well although some patients were late or did not show up for their appointment causing them to be unable to complete the EPDS due to time restraints. This decreased the sample size for this project because if a patient was late then the MDs and NP did not have the time necessary for the patient to complete the EPDS. Since the charts were flagged this cue helped the clerical staff

remember to give the EPDS to the patients. All 21 of the patients that were offered the EPDS voluntarily completed it and the MDs and NP denied problems using the scale.

The findings support the use of the EPDS by the three participating MDs and one NP in the ambulatory psychiatric clinic. These results show that the EPDS was feasible and clinically appropriate at this psychiatric clinic because it was easy to implement and helped prevent the misdiagnosis of PPD by positively identifying it. The three participating MDs and one NP decided to integrate the EPDS into their individual practice.

FUTURE RESEARCH

As previously discussed, a single clinic for the project was a limitation that may be addressed by implementing this project at multiple psychiatric ambulatory clinics with larger sample sizes. Future projects should include a longitudinal design to assess for lasting change with the use of the EPDS. The investigator plans to expand its use among more MDs and NPs as well as include Marriage Family Therapists and Licensed Clinical Social Workers at this psychiatric ambulatory clinic.

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APPENDIX A
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 3

Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale Articles

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion/Study Limitations/Strengths
To investigate evidence on the effectiveness of screening for PPD in WBC settings on mother and child outcomes (Van der Zee-van den Berg et al., 2017).	Systematic Review	Two reviewers independently performed study selection. Data extraction based on a predefined data extraction form. Pre-post design. Quasi-experimental. RCTs.	EPDS as the screening tool; cut-off scores of $\geq 10 - 12$. PHQ-9 as the screening tool; cut-off score ≥ 10 .	Six studies were included; a quality assessment rated two studies strong and four weak.	Promising evidence for the effectiveness of screening for PPD on maternal health outcomes but not the child. The use of the EPDS in all the included studies were significantly higher in detection of mothers with depression or When screening was combined with enhanced care, to improve depression scores. A limited number of studies in this review.

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion/Study Limitations/Strengths
					The most relevant articles were included in the review.
To determine the effectiveness of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) on PPD (Van Lieshout et al., 2017)	Quantitative descriptive design. IV: CBT DV: PPW	34 women with PDD completed a nine-week CBT group intervention.	EPDS as a screening tool for PPD.	Mean of pre-CBT scores on EPDS = 16.7 Mean of post CBT scores on EPDS = 9.4 Significantly decrease in EPDS score after completing CBT (p = 0.001).	CBT intervention showed a decrease in depressive symptoms, and significant improvements in social support, mother-infant bonding, and partner relationship quality. Patient satisfaction with CBT intervention was high. CBT intervention was clinically significant by 80% of participants in decreasing depressive symptoms. The sample size was relatively small. There was no pre and post control group. The group intervention and its manual were easy to use making it feasible.

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion/Study Limitations/Strengths
The Benefits of screening and treatment of PPD (O'Connor et al., 2016).	Systemic Review	Two investigators independently reviewed 6536 titles and abstracts, 478 full-text articles utilizing prespecified inclusion criteria.	EPDS PHQ-9 CBT	<p>6 trials (n = 11,869) showed 18% - 59% reductions, in the risk of depression at follow-up (3-5 months) with depression screening (EPDS and PHQ-9).</p> <p>23 studies (n = 5398), EPDS demonstrated sensitivity ranging from 0.67 (95%CI, 0.18-0.96) to 1.00 (95%CI, 0.67-1.00) and specificity consistently 0.87 or higher.</p> <p>Data was sparse for the Patient Health Questionnaire tools.</p> <p>CBT for PPW women with screen-detected depression showed They were more likely to have remission (pooled relative risk, 1.34 [95%CI, 1.19-1.50]).</p>	<p>Screening PPW for depression may reduce depressive symptoms and prevalence.</p> <p>Insufficient research on the PHQ-9.</p> <p>Strong sample size providing evidence that a sufficient number of participants were included.</p>
To identify socio-demographic, psychosocial and obstetrical risk factors	Prospective design. IV: Depression during pregnancy	312 pregnant outpatients in a single maternity unit.	The first assessment at 32 and 41 weeks' gestation with the EPDS.	Final sample of 264 women, 44 (16.7%) had postpartum depression	Non-obstetrical risk factors; depression during pregnancy, migrant status, and

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion/Study Limitations/Strengths
of postpartum depression in a middle-class community (Gaillard et al., 2014)	Migrant status Physical abuse. DV: PPW.		EPDS Six and eight weeks after delivery. EPDS cut-off score 12/30.	and 44 (16.7%) had antenatal depression defined by an EDPS \geq 12. 19 (7.2%) patients presented with both antenatal and postpartum depression. Out of 44 women with Postpartum depression, 82.4% had DSM-5 diagnostic criteria for major depression meaning a high validity of EPDS as a diagnostic tool for PPD.	history of physical abuse are independently associated with PPD. Obstetrical risk factors; physical complications stayed significant, controlling for antenatal depression Limitation: EPDS is a self-reported and can be overestimated regarding diagnosing PPD. Social support, life stressors, past history of depression and family history of depression were not assessed. Strength: The use of a prospective design.
To review the evidence on the efficacy of IPT for PPD (Miniati et al., 2014)	Systemic Review	11 primary clinical trials assessing the efficacy of IPT for PPD Total sample size of 544. RCTs Quasi-randomized clinical trial.	EPDS BDI HRSD	Based on the systemic review 20 patients out of 35 (57 %) that received IPT recovered.	IPT studies showed overall clinical improvement. Data suggests that the best time to start the intervention of IPT is during the acute depressive phase.

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion/Study Limitations/Strengths
		Open trial.			<p>IPT is not associated with rapid remission however, it leads to better mid-term/long-term outcomes.</p> <p>Limitations: Participants were mainly white in stable relationships with a partner and educated.</p> <p>Strengths: The presence of a strong comparison group.</p>
To compare the EPDS and the PHQ-9 in pregnant and postpartum women (Flynn et al., 2011)	<p>Quantitative correlational design.</p> <p>IV: EPDS and PHQ-9</p> <p>DV: pregnant and postpartum women.</p>	<p>Perinatal women from a large health care system.</p> <p>81 pregnant and 104 postpartum women (n=185).</p>	<p>EPDS cut-off score ≥ 13</p> <p>PHQ-9 cut-off score ≥ 10</p>	<p>Pearson correlations between the EPDS and PHQ-9 with strong summary scoring that was significant for both for pregnant [r (79) =0.718, p = 0.001] and postpartum [r (102) =0.769, p = 0.001] groups.</p> <p>Both instruments demonstrated adequate and similar internal consistency reliability.</p>	<p>There were few significant differences in the comparison of the PHQ-9 and EPDS in detecting depression pregnant and PPW.</p> <p>Limitations: Diagnostic information may not be accurately documented in the medical record causing diagnostic inaccuracy.</p> <p>Strengths: Rare information on depression screening</p>

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion/Study Limitations/Strengths
				<p>Cronbach's coefficient alphas for the EPDS were 0.86 and 0.84 for pregnant and postpartum women.</p> <p>Summary scoring for the PHQ-9 coefficients for pregnant and postpartum women was 0.87 and 0.85.</p>	measures with pregnant and PPW.
To conduct a parallel-group RCT to determine the efficacy of TAICBT for the treatment of PPD (Pugh et al., 2016).	<p>RCT</p> <p>IV: TAICBT</p> <p>DV: Women with PPD</p>	<p>50 women who gave birth to an infant in the past year</p> <p>From Saskatchewan, Canada.</p>	<p>Scored > 10 on the EPDS.</p> <p>The efficacy of the treatment was investigated at baseline, seven and ten-week follow-up.</p> <p>Participants were randomly assigned to receive either TAICBT (n = 25) or waitlist control (n = 25).</p>	<p>PPD symptoms decreased more for participants in the TAICBT group averaging a reduction of 6.24 points on the EPDS.</p> <p>Participants in the waitlist control group averaged a reduction of 2.42 points on the EPDS.</p> <p>Results were significant and maintained at a four-week follow-up.</p> <p>TAICBT participants also had a reduction in postnatal anxiety, general stress and</p>	<p>TAICBT is an effective, well-utilized, and desirable intervention for women with PPD.</p> <p>It is effective at reducing symptoms of PPD, parental stress, and improved psychological and environmental quality of life.</p> <p>Limitations: Further investigation for TAICBT for PPD is required to compare TAICBT to an active control condition.</p>

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion/Study Limitations/Strengths
				parental distress. and An increase in psychological and environmental quality of life compared to the waitlist control participants.	A larger and more heterogeneous sample size. Strengths: High rate of symptom recovery in PPD for the mother.
To test the feasibility, effectiveness, and acceptability of CNM-IPT to treat PPD (Posmontier et al., 2016).	Prospective cohort design	Women that met DSM-5 criteria for depression was recruited from eight obstetric practices in the United States. 41 women in the treatment group received up to eight 50-minute IPT sessions and 20 in the control group were referred to mental health professionals.	HRSD. Maternal and marital functioning. Mother-infant bonding. Social support. Client satisfaction.	HRSDs at 8 and 12 weeks was significantly lower among women in the treatment group compared to the control group. (Week 8, $P = .047$; Week 12, $P = .029$). Client satisfaction was high in both groups. While only 5 out of 8 CNM-IPT counselors continued the intervention until the study's conclusion, CNM-IPT counselor protocol adherence was high.	CNMs can provide effective psychotherapy over the phone and can be effective members of a multidisciplinary mental health team. CNM-IPT is an effective method in reducing the severity of PPD. CNM availability is important for feasibility. Future research is needed to evaluate translation of this intervention into practice. Limitation: small sample size and no randomization.

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion/Study Limitations/Strengths
					<p>Strengths: previous studies have not evaluated specialized psychotherapy training for CNMs that was accomplished in this study.</p> <p>80% power in detecting a medium Cohen's d effect size of 0.78 statistically significant at the alpha equals .05 level for the primary outcome.</p>
To examine the efficacy of IPT in reducing the risk of PPD in pregnant women.	RCT	<p>205 pregnant women.</p> <p>18 years old or older, on public assistance, and at risk for PPD.</p> <p>38% Hispanic and 23% Black were randomized to either the IPT group intervention (104) or the treatment as usual control program (101).</p>	<p>Longitudinal Interview Follow-up Examination.</p> <p>Psychiatric Status Ratings.</p>	<p>At six months depression rate in the intervention group (16%) was lower than the control group (31%), and the effect of the intervention was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.</p>	<p>IPT intervention during the prenatal period has the reduced cases of PPD within six months postpartum in at-risk mothers on public assistance.</p> <p>Limitation: findings may not be will generalizable to a more heterogeneous sample of women, Such as women from a range of socio-economic and cultural backgrounds, or marital status.</p>

Purpose (Author, Date)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusion/Study Limitations/Strengths
					<p>Strengths: this was a longitudinal study that replicated positive findings previous trials.</p> <p>This study included ethnically diverse community-based sample.</p>

Note: BDI = Beck Depression Inventory; CNM-IPT = Certified Nurse-Midwife Telephone-Administered Interpersonal Psychotherapy; CBT = Cognitive Behavioral Therapy; DSM-5 = Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders; EPDS = Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale; IPT = Interpersonal Therapy; HRDS = Hamilton Rating Scale for Depression; MDD = Major Depressive Disorder; PHQ-9 = Patient Health Questionnaire; PPD = Postpartum Depression; PPW = Postpartum Women; RCTs = Randomized Control Trials; TAICBT = Therapist-Assisted Internet-delivered Cognitive Behavior Therapy; WBC = Well Baby Care.